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FREE- REFERENCE IMAGE QUALITY ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK USING METRICS FUSION AND DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on no-reference image quality assessment(NR-IQA)metrics. In the literature, a wide range of algorithms are proposed to automatically estimate the perceived quality of visual data. However, most of them are not able to effectively quantify the various degradations and artifacts that the image may undergo. Thus, merging of diverse metrics operating in different information domains is hoped to yield better performances, which is the main theme of the proposed work. In particular, the metric proposed in this paper is based on three well-known NR-IQA objective metrics that depend on natural scene statistical attributes from three different domains to extract a vector of image features. Then, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) based dominant eigenvectors method is used to select the most relevant image quality attributes. These latter are used as input to Relevance Vector Machine (RVM) to derive the overall quality index. Validation experiments are divided into two groups; in the first group, learning process (training and test phases) is applied on one single image quality database whereas in the second group of simulations, training and test phases are separated on two distinct datasets. Obtained results demonstrate that the proposed metric performs very well in terms of correlation, monotonicity and accuracy in both the two scenarios.

KEYWORDS

Image quality assessment, metrics fusion, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), dominant eigenvectors, dimensionality reduction, Relevance Vector Machine (RVM)

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Zhang, Y. Ding, N. Zheng, "[Nature scene statistics approach based on ICA for no-reference image quality assessment](#)", Proceedings of International Workshop on Information and Electronics Engineering (IWIEE), 29 (2012), 3589- 3593.
- [2] A. K. Moorthy, A. C. Bovik, "[A two-step framework for constructing blind image quality indices](#)", IEEE Signal Process. Lett., 17 (2010), 513-516.
- [3] L. Zhang, L. Zhang, A.C. Bovik, "[A Feature-Enriched Completely Blind Image Quality Evaluator](#)", IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 24(8) (2015), 2579- 2591.
- [4] M.A. Saad, A.C. Bovik, C. Charrier, "[A DCT statistics-based blind image quality index](#)", Signal Process. Lett. 17 (2010) 583–586.
- [5] M. A. Saad, A. C. Bovik, C. Charrier, "[Blind image quality assessment: A natural scene statistics approach in the DCT domain](#)", IEEE Trans. Image Process., 21 (2012), 3339-3352.
- [6] A. Mittal, A.K. Moorthy, A.C. Bovik, "[No-reference image quality assessment in the spatial domain](#)", IEEE Trans. Image Process. 21 (2012), 4695 - 4708.
- [7] A. Mittal, R. Soundararajan, A. C. Bovik, "[Making a completely blind image quality analyzer](#)", IEEE Signal Process. Lett., 20 (2013), 209-212.
- [8] N. Kruger, P. Janssen, S. Kalkan, M. Lappe, A. Leonardis, J. Piater, A. Rodriguez-Sanchez, L. Wiskott, "[Deep hierarchies in the primate visual cortex: What can we learn for computer vision?](#)", IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell., 35 (2013), 1847–1871.
- [9] D. J. Felleman, D. C. Van Essen, "[Distributed hierarchical processing in the primate cerebral cortex](#)", "Distributed hierarchical processing in the primate cerebral cortex,"
- [10] B. Sadou, A. Lahoulou, T. Bouden, "[A New No-reference Color Image Quality Assessment Metric in Wavelet and Gradient Domains](#)", 6th International Conference on Control Engineering and Information Technologies, Istanbul, Turkey, 25-27 October (2018), 954-959.
- [11] Q. Wu, H. Li, F. Meng, K. N. Ngan, S. Zhu, "[No reference image quality assessment metric via multi-domain structural information and piecewise regression](#)", J. Vis. Commun. Image R., 32(2015), 205–216.
- [12] X. Shang, X. Zhao, Y. Ding, "[Image quality assessment based on joint quality-aware representation construction in multiple domains](#)", Journal of Engineering 4 (2018), 1-12.
- [13] B. Sadou, A.Lahoulou, T.Bouden, A.R. Avila, T.H. Falk, Z. Akhtar, "[Blind Image Quality Assessment Using Singular Value Decomposition Based Dominant Eigenvectors for Feature Selection](#)", 5th Int. Conf. on Signal and Image Processing (SIPRO'19), Toronto, Canada, pp. 233-242, 2019.
- [14] H. R. Sheikh, Z. Wang, L. Cormack, A. C. Bovik, LIVE Image Quality Assessment Database Release 2 (2005), <http://live.ece.utexas.edu/research/quality>
- [15] E. Larson, D. M. Chandler, Categorical image quality assessment (CSIQ) database.<http://vision.okstate.edu/?loc=csiq>

- [16] M. W. Mahoney, P. Drineas, “[CUR matrix decompositions for improved data analysis](#),” in Proc. the National Academy of Sciences, February 2009.
- [17] M.E. Tipping. The relevance vector machines. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 12, Solla SA, Leen TK, Muller K-R (eds). MIT Press: Cambridge, MA (2000), 652-658.
- [18] D. Basak, S. Pal, D.C. Patranabis, Support vector regression, Neural Information Processing – Letters and Reviews, 11 (2007).
- [19] B. SchÖlkopf, A.J. Smola, Learning with Kernels. MIT press, Cambridge, (2002).
- [20] Final VQEG report on the validation of objective quality metrics for video quality assessment: http://www.its.bldrdoc.gov/vqeg/projects/frtv_phaseI/
- [21] H. R. Sheikh, M. F. Sabir, A. C. Bovik, [A statistical evaluation of recent full reference image quality assessment algorithms](#), IEEE Trans. Image Process., 15 (2006), 3440–3451.

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TEST-COST-SENSITIVE CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS WITH EXPERT BRANCHES

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ABSTRACT

It has been proven that deeper convolutional neural networks (CNN) can result in better accuracy in many problems, but this accuracy comes with a high computational cost. Also, input instances have not the same difficulty. As a solution for accuracy vs. computational cost dilemma, we introduce a new test-cost-sensitive method for convolutional neural networks. This method trains a CNN with a set of auxiliary outputs and expert branches in some middle layers of the network. The expert branches decide to use a shallower part of the network or going deeper to the end, based on the difficulty of input instance. The expert branches learn to determine: is the current network prediction is wrong and if the given instance passed to deeper layers of the network it will generate right output; If not, then the expert branches stop the computation process. The experimental results on standard dataset CIFAR-10 show that the proposed method can train models with lower test-cost and competitive accuracy in comparison with basic models.

KEYWORDS

Test-Cost-Sensitive Learning; Deep Learning; CNN with Expert Branches; Instance-Based Cost

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. P. S. Gurjar, S. Gupta, and R. Srivastava, "[Automatic Image Annotation Model Using LSTM Approach](#)," Signal Image Process. An Int. J., vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 25–37, Aug. 2017.
- [2] S. Maity, M. Abdel-Mottaleb, and S. S. As, "[Multimodal Biometrics Recognition from Facial Video via Deep Learning](#)," in Computer Science & Information Technology (CS & IT), 2017, pp. 67–75.
- [3] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition," arXiv Prepr. arXiv1512.03385, 2015.
- [4] D. Kadam, A. R. Madane, K. Kutty, and B. S.V, "[Rain Streaks Elimination Using Image Processing Algorithms](#)," Signal Image Process. An Int. J., vol. 10, no. 03, pp. 21–32, Jun. 2019.
- [5] A. Massaro, V. Vitti, and A. Galiano, "[Automatic Image Processing Engine Oriented on Quality Control of Electronic Boards](#)," Signal Image Process. An Int. J., vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 01–14, Apr. 2018.
- [6] X. Li, Z. Liu, P. Luo, C. Change Loy, and X. Tang, "Not all pixels are equal: Difficulty-aware semantic segmentation via deep layer cascade," in Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2017, pp. 3193–3202.
- [7] M. Naghibi, R. Anvari, A. Forghani, and B. Minaei, "[Cost-Sensitive Topical Data Acquisition from the Web](#)," Int. J. Data Min. Knowl. Manag. Process, vol. 09, no. 03, pp. 39–56, May 2019.
- [8] A. Polyak and L. Wolf, "[Channel-Level Acceleration of Deep Face Representations](#)," Access, IEEE, vol. 3, pp. 2163–2175, 2015.
- [9] A. Lavin and S. Gray, "[Fast Algorithms for Convolutional Neural Networks](#)," in 2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2016, pp. 4013–4021.
- [10] J. Ba and R. Caruana, "Do deep nets really need to be deep?," in Advances in neural information processing systems, 2014, pp. 2654–2662.
- [11] A. Romero, N. Ballas, S. E. Kahou, A. Chassang, C. Gatta, and Y. Bengio, "[Fitnets: Hints for thin deep nets](#)," arXiv Prepr. arXiv1412.6550, 2014.
- [12] X. Zhang, J. Zou, K. He, and J. Sun, "[Accelerating very deep convolutional networks for classification and detection](#)," 2015.
- [13] E. L. Denton, W. Zaremba, J. Bruna, Y. LeCun, and R. Fergus, "[Exploiting linear structure within convolutional networks for efficient evaluation](#)," in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 2014, pp. 1269–1277.
- [14] M. Jaderberg, A. Vedaldi, and A. Zisserman, "[Speeding up convolutional neural networks with low rank expansions](#)," arXiv Prepr. arXiv1405.3866, 2014.
- [15] N. Ström, "[Sparse connection and pruning in large dynamic artificial neural networks](#)," in EUROSPEECH, 1997.
- [16] G. E. Hinton, N. Srivastava, A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and R. R. Salakhutdinov, "[Improving neural networks by preventing co-adaptation of feature detectors](#)," arXiv Prepr. arXiv1207.0580, 2012.

- [17] N. Vasilache, J. Johnson, M. Mathieu, S. Chintala, S. Piantino, and Y. LeCun, “[Fast convolutional nets with fbfft: A GPU performance evaluation](#),” arXiv Prepr. arXiv1412.7580, 2014.
- [18] M. Mathieu, M. Henaff, and Y. LeCun, “[Fast training of convolutional networks through FFTs](#),” arXiv Prepr. arXiv1312.5851, 2013.
- [19] V. N. Murthy, V. Singh, T. Chen, R. Manmatha, and D. Comaniciu, “[Deep decision network for multi-class image classification](#),” in Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2016, pp. 2240–2248.
- [20] V. Vanhoucke, A. Senior, and M. Z. Mao, “[Improving the speed of neural networks on CPUs](#),” in Proc. Deep Learning and Unsupervised Feature Learning NIPS Workshop, 2011, vol. 1.
- [21] A. Toshev and C. Szegedy, “[Deeppose: Human pose estimation via deep neural networks](#),” in Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2014, pp. 1653–1660.
- [22] A. Krizhevsky, G. Hinton, and others, “[Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images](#),” 2009.
- [23] C. Szegedy, V. Vanhoucke, S. Ioffe, J. Shlens, and Z. Wojna, “[Rethinking the inception architecture for computer vision](#),” in Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2016, pp. 2818–2826.
- [24] M. Abadi, A. Agarwal, P. Barham, E. Brevdo, Z. Chen, C. Citro, G. S. Corrado, A. Davis, J. Dean, M. Devin, S. Ghemawat, I. Goodfellow, A. Harp, G. Irving, M. Isard, Y. Jia, R. Jozefowicz, L. Kaiser, M. Kudlur, J. Levenberg, D. Mane, R. Monga, S. Moore, D. Murray, C. Olah, M. Schuster, J. Shlens, B. Steiner, I. Sutskever, K. Talwar, P. Tucker, V. Vanhoucke, V. Vasudevan, F. Viegas, O. Vinyals, P. Warden, M. Wattenberg, M. Wicke, Y. Yu, and X. Zheng, “TensorFlow: Large-Scale Machine Learning on Heterogeneous Distributed Systems,” Mar. 2016.

ROBUST IMAGE WATERMARKING METHOD USING WAVELET TRANSFORM

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a robust watermarking method operating in the wavelet domain for grayscale digital images is developed. The method first computes the differences between the watermark and the HH1 sub-band of the cover image values and then embed these differences in one of the frequency sub-bands. The results show that embedding the watermark in the LH1 sub-band gave the best results. The results were evaluated using the RMSE and the PSNR of both the original and the watermarked image. Although the watermark was recovered perfectly in the ideal case, the addition of Gaussian noise, or compression of the image using JPEG with quality less than 100 destroys the embedded watermark. Different experiments were carried out to test the performance of the proposed method and good results were obtained.

KEYWORDS

Watermarking, data hiding, wavelet transform, frequency domain

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Dugelay and S. Roche, "[A survey of current watermarking techniques](#)", in S. Katzenbeisser and F. Petitcolas (eds), Information hiding techniques for steganography and digital watermarking, Artech House, USA, pp. 121-148, 2000.
- [2] I. Cox, M. Miller, J. Bloom, J. Fridrich and T. Kalker "[Digital watermarking and steganography](#)", Morgan Kaufman, 2008.
- [3] R. Gonzalez, R. Woods, Digital Image Processing, 3rd ed., Prentice Hall, 2008..
- [4] M. Kutter and F. Hartung, "[Introduction to Watermarking Techniques](#)", in S. Katzenbeisser and F. Petitcolas (eds), Information hiding techniques for steganography and digital watermarking, Artech House, USA, pp. 97-120, 2000.
- [5] S. Lai and F. Buonaiuti, "Copyright on the internet and watermarking", in S. Katzenbeisser and F. Petitcolas (eds), Information hiding techniques for steganography and digital watermarking, Artech House, USA, pp. 191-213, 2000.
- [6] I. Cox, M.L. Miller, J.M.G. Linnartz, T. Kalker, "[A Review of Watermarking Principles and Practices](#)" in Digital Signal Processing for Multimedia Systems, K.K. Parhi, T. Nishitani, eds., New York, New York, Marcel Dekker, Inc., 1999, pp. 461-482.
- [7] U. Qidwai and C. Chen, Digital image processing: An algorithmic approach with Matlab, CRC Press, 2010.
- [8] Cox, M. Miller, J. Kilian, F. Leighton and T. Shamoan, "[Secure spread spectrum watermarking for multimedia](#)", IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, Vol. 6, No. 12, pp. 1673-1687, 1997.
- [9] N. Johnson and S. Katzenbeisser, "[A survey of steganographic techniques](#)," in S. Katzenbeisser and F. Petitcolas (eds), Information hiding techniques for steganography and digital watermarking, Artech House, USA, pp. 43-78, 2000.
- [10] A.H.M. Jaffar Iqbal Barbhuiya1 , K. Hemachandran (2013), "[Wavelet Transformations & Its Major Applications In Digital Image Processing](#)", International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) Vol. 2 Issue 3, March - 2013 ISSN: 2278-0181
- [11] Khan, Asifullah; Mirza, Anwar M. (October 2007). "[Genetic perceptual shaping: Utilizing cover image and conceivable attack information during watermark embedding](#)". Information Fusion. 8 (4): 354-365. doi:10.1016/j.inffus.2005.09.007.
- [12] C. Shoemaker, Hidden Bits: "[A Survey of Techniques for Digital Watermarking](#)", <http://www.vu.union.edu/~shoemak/watermarking/>, 2002. Last access: June, 2012.
- [13] M. Weeks, "Digital signal processing using Matlab and Wavelets, 2nd ed.", Jones and Bartlett publisher, 2011.
- [14] D. Kundur and D. Hatzinakos, "[A robust digital watermarking method using wavelet-based fusion](#)", in Proceeding of the International conference on image processing, Santa Barbara, pp. 544-547, 1997.
- [15] X. Xia, C. Boncelet and G. Arce, "[Wavelet transform based watermark for digital images](#)", Optics Express, Vol. 3, No. 12, pp. 497-511, 1998.

- [16] O. Adwan, et al., "[Simple Image Watermarking Method using Wavelet Transform](#)", Journal of Basic and Applied Science, Vol. 8, No. 17, pp. 98-101, 2014.
- [17] B. Gunjal and S. Mali, "[Secured color image watermarking technique in DWT-DCT domain](#)", International journal of computer science, engineering and information technology, Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 36-44, 2011.
- [18] P. Reddy, M. Prasad and D. Rao, "[Robust digital watermarking of images using wavelets](#)", International journal of computer and electrical engineering, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 111-116, 2011.
- [19] G. Langelaar, I. Setyawan, R.L. Lagendijk, "Watermarking Digital Image and Video Data", in IEEE Signal Processing Magazine, Vol. 17, pp. 20-43, 2000.
- [20] Tanya Koochpayeh Araghi, Azizah B T Abdul Manaf (2017), "[Evaluation of Digital Image Watermarking Techniques](#)", International Conference of Reliable Information and Communication Technology, IRICT 2017: Recent Trends in Information and Communication Technology pp 361-368.
- [21] A.S.Kapse¹, Sharayu Belokar², Yogita Gorde³, Radha Rane⁴, Shrutika Yewtkar, (2018) "[Digital Image Security Using Digital Watermarking](#)". International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Volume: 05 Issue: 03 | Mar-2018.

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IMPROVEMENTS OF THE ANALYSIS OF HUMAN ACTIVITY USING ACCELERATION RECORD OF ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHS

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ABSTRACT

The use of Holter Electrocardiograph (Holter ECG) is rapidly spreading. It is a wearable electrocardiograph that records 24-hour electrocardiograms in a built-in flash memory, making it possible to detect atrial fibrillation (Atrial Fibrillation, AF) through all-day activities. It is also useful for screening for diseases other than atrial fibrillation and for improving health. It is said that more useful information can be obtained by combining electrocardiograph with the analysis of physical activity. For that purpose, the Holter electrocardiograph is equipped with heart rate sensor and acceleration sensors. If acceleration data is analysed, we can estimate activities in daily life, such as getting up, eating, walking, using transportation, and sitting. In combination with such activity status, electrocardiographic data can be expected to be more useful.

In this study, we investigate the estimation of physical activity. For the better analysis, we evaluated activity estimation using machine learning as well as several different feature extractions. In this report, we will show several different feature extraction methods and result of human body analysis using machine learning.

KEYWORDS

Wearable, Biomedical Sensors, Body Activity, Machine Learning

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REFERENCES

- [1] Yuda E, Hayano J, [Menstrual Cycles of Autonomic Functions and Physical Activities](#), 2018 9th International Conference on Awareness Science and Technology (iCAST 2018), September 19- 21, (2018)
- [2] Hayano J, *Introduction to heart rate variability*. In: Iwase S, Hayano J, Orimo S, eds *Clinical assessment of the autonomic nervous system*. Japan.
- [3] Yuda E, Furukawa Y, Yoshida Y, Hayano J, ALLSTAR Research Group, *Association between Regional Difference in Heart Rate Variability and Inter-prefecture Ranking of Healthy Life Expectancy: ALLSTAR Big Data Project in Japan*, *Proceedings of the 7th EAI International Conference on Big Data Technologies and Applications (BDTA)*, Chung-ang University, Seoul, South Korea, November 17-18 (2016)
- [4] YOSHIHARA Hiroyuki, *gEHR Project: Nation - wide EHR Implementation in JAPAN*, *Kyoto Smart city Expo*, https://expo.smartcity.kyoto/2016/doc/ksce2016_doc_yoshihara.pdf (captured on 2016)
- [5] J Jaybhay, R Shastri, *A study of speckle noise reduction Filters*|| *Signal & Image Processing, SIPJ* Vol. 6,2015
- [6] Mrs V.Radhika1 & Dr G. Padmavathi , *Performance of various order statistics filters in impulse and mixed noise removal for rs images*, *SIPIJ*, Vol. 1, No. 2, December 2010

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